

Uranium(IV) complexes of Schiff bases derived from 2-aminopyridine

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Uranium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases obtained by condensing 2-aminopyridine with various substituted salicylaldehydes, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxynaphthalidene have been prepared. A coordination number of eight is suggested for these complexes.

In continuation of our study on uranium(IV) complexes¹⁻⁴, herein we report the synthesis of uranium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases (Fig. 1) derived from 2-aminopyridine and various aldehydes, ketones and 2-hydroxynaphthalidene-2-aminopyridine (2-OH NapAP).

Abbr	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄
SAP	H	H	H	H
5-Me-SAP	H	H	Me	H
4-Me-SAP	H	Me	H	H
5-Cl-SAP	H	H	Cl	H
5-Br-SAP	H	H	Br	H
3-OMe-SAP	OMe	H	H	H
<i>o</i> -OH-Acf AP	H	H	H	CH ₃

Fig. 1

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes are consistent with 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The complexes were found insoluble in common organic solvents, viz. acetone, chloroform, benzene, ethanol and methanol, but soluble in hot DMF and DMSO. They decomposed without melting above 320°. The lower conductivity values (25–34 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) suggest non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The magnetic moment values are in close agreement with the spin-only values for the presence of two unpaired electrons and thus the possibility of metal-metal interaction is ruled out. The complexes were stable upto 8 weeks *in vacuo* and then led to a slow oxidation of U^{IV} to U^{VI} as indicated by

slow decrease in magnetic moment values measured every 4 days. This is in line with our previous observations¹⁻⁴ that the stability of U^{IV} increases on complexation with oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands. The oxidation is fast in air compared to that *in vacuo*.

The ligands revealed IR bands at 2800–2700 (intramolecular H-bonded OH), 1605 (azomethine C=N) and 1585 cm^{-1} (pyridine C=N). On complexation, the ligand band due to H-bonded OH disappeared, indicating the destruction of H-bonding. The appearance of a broad non-ligand band at 3400–3380 cm^{-1} suggests the coordination of the ligand through oxygen of hydroxy group. The ligand band at 1290–1280 cm^{-1} (phenolic C–O) suffered a positive shift by 50–30 cm^{-1} in the complexes suggesting the coordination of oxygen of *o*-OH group of the Schiff bases. The band due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (azomethine) suffered a positive shift by 5–10 cm^{-1} with decreased intensity indicating its coordination. The observed blue-shift indicates an increase in bond order upon complexation³. The absorbance due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (pyridine) remained unaffected suggesting its non-involvement in coordination. The ν_{asym} (OCO) (ν_8) and ν_{sym} (OCO) (ν_3) modes of acetate moieties were observed at 1570 and 1210 cm^{-1} , respectively, and their extent of separation indicates that acetate moieties are coordinated in unidentate fashion⁵.

Gans *et al.*⁶ studied the reflectance spectra of a series of uranium(IV) complexes and divided them into three classes based on intensities of the bands on the arbitrary Beckman scale as 'weak intensity type', 'medium intensity type' and 'strong intensity type'. Based on this classification, the reflectance spectra of the present U^{IV} complexes belong to 'medium intensity type' and resemble closely with those of six-coordinated U^{IV} complexes^{6,7} with *cis*-octahedral environment which lacks centre of symmetry. Hence the spectral bands are not only vibronic in origin but also electronic in origin. The transitions along with their assignments are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Electronic (reflectance) spectral data (λ_{\max} , nm)

Term	[U(SAP)Ac ₄]	[U(3-OMeSAP)Ac ₄]	[U(o-OH-MeSAP)Ac ₄]
³ H ₅	1525	1530	1532
	1390	1380	1380
³ F ₄	1150	1160	1150
³ F ₃	1070	1070	1070
³ H ₆	800	800	800
³ P ₀	645	645	645
¹ I ₆	500	-	470
³ P ₂	410	410	400

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Substituted salicylaldehydes⁸, *o*-hydroxyl acetophenone-2-aminopyridine⁹ and their Schiff bases were prepared by reported methods¹⁰. Uranium(IV) acetate was prepared by the reduction of uranyl acetate with zinc amalgam¹¹.

The complexes were prepared by refluxing a mixture of uranium(IV) acetate (0.01 mol) and the Schiff base (0.01 mol) in dry benzene under nitrogen atmosphere with stirring for 2 h. The separated complexes were washed with dry benzene, dried and stored under vacuum over P₂O₅.

The complexes were analyzed for uranium and halogens by standard methods¹². C, H and N were determined by microanalytical method. The molar conductance was measured in DMF at 10⁻³ M concentration using a Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge. Magnetic moment was measured at room temperature on Gouy balance and diamag-

netic corrections were made by direct weighing of the ligand for diamagnetic pull. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 787 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Cary d-2390 spectrophotometer.

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